

MODERN SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE QASHQADARYO REGION

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Annotation: The content of the article is focused on the poorly developed areas of tourism infrastructure in the Qashqadaryo region, as well as the problems related to transport and movement routes that arise in tourist centers with potential. It includes proposals and reflections on their solutions.

Keywords: Infrastructure, horse and cart, investment, profit, tourist centers, travel agencies, enjoyment, communication, low cost, long duration.

Introduction

Currently, tourism is one of the rapidly developing sectors in all countries of the world. Therefore, special attention is being paid to the development of tourism in Uzbekistan, and measures are being implemented to improve tourism infrastructure.

In particular, in accordance with the state program for the implementation of the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026, approved by the Presidential Decree No. PF-60 of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022, and the initiative of the "Year of Honoring Human Dignity and Active Mahalla," as well as the goal of further improving the tourism infrastructure to ensure that people with disabilities can travel comfortably across the country, the following key areas for the development of an accessible tourism infrastructure in the Republic of Uzbekistan are established:

- Creating the necessary conditions for the free movement of individuals with disabilities in tourism industry facilities, cultural organizations, and cultural heritage sites, including museums, theaters, and accommodation facilities.

- Encouraging tourism sector entities, including tour operators and travel agents, owners of accommodation facilities, and entrepreneurs providing transport services, as well as citizens who accompany individuals with disabilities during their travels.

- Increasing awareness among individuals with disabilities about the opportunities created in our republic for barrier-free travel through extensive promotion.

- Improving the quality of services provided to individuals with disabilities at tourism industry facilities by utilizing modern information and communication technology.[1]

This decision can serve as a clear example of such initiatives. Therefore, it has been studied that the complete tourism infrastructure in our country has not been fully developed and the specific areas where the tourism infrastructure is lacking have been identified, along with proposed solutions.

Analysis of Literature and Methodology

Let's first focus on what tourism infrastructure is. Tourism infrastructure refers to the extensive use of tourism resources and the understanding of the roads leading to tourist sites. This includes the regulation of the systems of highways, railways, air routes, as well as sea and river routes. It is well known that tourism cannot be developed without tourism resources. Only when tourism infrastructure is created based on these resources can the tourism sector develop extensively. For instance, tourism infrastructure can be developed in areas that have natural-climatic, historical-cultural, and social-recreational tourist attractions.

We can take the road construction sector as an example. Tourists are not ordinary passengers; therefore, roads must meet modern requirements. The

smoothness of roads also leads to an increase in the number of tourists. Roads and markets indicate the economic and cultural status of a country. This applies not only to highways but also to railway lines. All communication and engineering networks on trains are considered part of tourism. Tourists are consumers who desire high-quality services and are entitled to them. Especially, improving the road infrastructure in remote mountainous areas requires significant investments.

Currently, the condition of roadside facilities on the highways in our republic does not meet the demands of foreign tourists. Addressing this issue has become a modern requirement for the construction of infrastructure facilities. It is difficult to imagine tourism infrastructure without modern computer technologies. Quick information and communication awareness of news are an integral part of tourism. Today, the demand for tourists to use the Internet and other modern technologies indicates the level of tourism infrastructure.

Thus, having comprehensive information about tourism infrastructure, let's consider measures to improve this infrastructure using the example of the Kashkadarya region. First, we need to determine the tourism potential of the area.

In the Qashqadaryo region, 17.76% of all historical monuments in the Republic are located. Currently, there are 1,468 cultural heritage sites registered in the Qashqadaryo region, of which 1,189 are archaeological sites, 208 are architectural sites, 43 are monumental monuments, and 34 are attractions. According to the 9th clause of the Decree No. PF-6165 of February 9, 2021, titled "Measures to Further Develop Domestic and Pilgrimage Tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan," the Qashqadaryo regional administration has allocated 200 billion soums from the budget to improve tourism and infrastructure in the region. Additionally, several tourist areas can demonstrate their tourism potential.

For example:

- Qarshi city: 28 archaeological sites, 25 architectural monuments, 6 monumental art monuments, and 1 attraction.

- Shahrissabz district: 138 archaeological sites, 22 architectural monuments, and 5 monumental art monuments.
- Yakkabog' district: 195 archaeological sites, 38 architectural monuments, 2 monumental art monuments, and 2 attractions.
- Kitob district: 281 archaeological sites, 16 architectural monuments, 3 monumental art monuments, and 5 attractions.
- G'uzor district: 94 archaeological sites, 9 architectural monuments, 3 monumental art monuments, and 3 attractions.
- Koson district: 76 archaeological sites, 11 architectural monuments, 4 monumental art monuments, and 1 attraction.
- Chiroqchi district: 58 archaeological sites, 16 architectural monuments, 3 monumental art monuments, and 2 attractions.
- Shahrissabz city: 29 archaeological sites, 28 architectural monuments, and 5 monumental art monuments.
- Qarshi district: 58 archaeological sites, 29 architectural monuments, 28 monumental art monuments, and 5 attractions.
- Kasbi district: 79 archaeological sites, 11 architectural monuments, 2 monumental art monuments, and 2 attractions.
- Nishon district: 3 archaeological sites, 1 architectural monument, and 3 attractions.
- Mirishkor district: 9 archaeological sites, 6 architectural monuments, 2 monumental art monuments, and 1 attraction.
- Muborak district: 2 archaeological sites, 3 architectural monuments, 2 monumental art monuments, and 1 attraction.

The Qashqadaryo region is characterized by its foothill and mountainous areas. Specifically, Miroqi town, the Kitob State Nature Reserve, Hisor State Reserve, Ko'l, Varganza, and the village of Xazora have favorable climate conditions for health recovery.[2]

There are about 20 healing springs in the region, mainly found in the foothill and mountainous parts. Among them, the Zevardi, Maymanoq, Qarliq, O'rta, Muborak, and Xo'jaxayron springs are considered significant for the national economy. The springs contain chemical elements such as hydrocarbonate sodium, bromine, iodine, bromine oxide, sodium sulfate, and hydrogen sulfide.

A well-developed tourism spot in the Shahrisabz district is the village of Ko'l. This village is distinguished by its unique beauty and excellent climate. It is located in the high mountainous areas of the Shahrisabz district. The road leading to Ko'l village is quite long and primarily traverses rocky areas and deep gorges. About 1,500 people reside in Ko'l village, whose main livelihoods are local agriculture, animal husbandry, and providing services to tourists. The village receives a high amount of precipitation, with very cold winters and relatively cool summers. Throughout the year, the sun shines only for about four months, while the rest of the time it rains or snows. The roads leading to the village are primarily single-lane roads. Ethnographic and ecotourism sites are available in the region.

Another village in Shahrisabz district with significant tourism potential is G'ilon village. This village stands out with its uniqueness and wonderful air. It is situated at the foothills of the Hisor mountains. The local population engages in livestock farming and agriculture. The area has several ecotourism sites and recreational healing waters. About 7,000 people live in the village. Due to the prolonged winter, the village has seasonal tourism characteristics. One of the main problems in this village is its road infrastructure.[3]

Currently, the road leading to the "Langar ota" pilgrimage site and mosque, dating back to the 14th century, and the "Maydanak" observatory, located 176 km away from Qarshi city, is under study for improvements in electricity supply, water, and sewage infrastructure.

Currently, the "Bashir" village in the Kitob district of Qashqadaryo is being transformed into a tourism village. Many rapid works are underway in this regard.

It is worth noting that the "Hazrati Bashir" village is located by the Qashqadaryo gorge. Currently, there are more than 20 family guesthouses operating in the village. Pilgrimage tourism, ecotourism, and agrotourism are developing there. The "Hazrati Bashir" shrine is located in the village, named after the saint Hazrati Sultan Said Ahmad Bashir (1368-1464) who lived there. Many local and foreign tourists have been visiting this village, and their number is increasing year by year.

Currently, great attention is being paid to the tourism sector in Qashqadaryo region, and this sector is gradually developing. In our country, especially in Qashqadaryo region, the tourism potential is considered very high. The beautiful nature, climate, history, cultural monuments, and diversity in the culture of the regions all embody this potential.

In the Qashqadaryo region, the number of historical monuments is particularly high in the Shahrisabz, Qarshi, and Kitob districts. The city of Shahrisabz is included in UNESCO's World Heritage list. Due to its long history, the Qashqadaryo region has a diverse array of historical monuments and scientific innovations. The number of historical monuments varies across regions. The role of financial institutions and services is significant. It is well known that tourists wish to utilize various services during their travel and leisure. That is, they want to buy something at their own discretion. Carrying cash, especially large amounts, creates significant inconveniences for tourists. The fact that tourists carry large amounts of money can lead to crimes such as theft and robbery. With the emergence of tourism, the issue of ensuring tourists' safety with cash has arisen. Currently, this issue has found its solution through computer technologies, including visas and credit cards. Information services are also essential for both tourists and their organizers in tourism infrastructure. Tourists require maps of the places they are visiting and road schematics. Therefore, information in the tourism sector is vital.

Nowadays, various modes of transportation, including buses, air, and rail travel, have developed and advanced. Considering the growth rate of tourism and

its positive impact on the economy and overall well-being of the population, as well as the need for measures to protect the environment, the tourism sector should be one of the strongest tools for the sustainable growth of the country's development.

Currently, the shortcomings in transport and social infrastructure, the lack of convenient tourist information (navigation and information centers), the shortage of qualified personnel, and the weakness of promoting Uzbekistan abroad are serious ongoing issues.

To rapidly develop the tourism sector economically, organizationally, and legally, necessary measures are being taken to utilize the tourism potential of regions more effectively and to fundamentally improve the management of the tourism network. The Qashqadaryo region holds a significant place in the development of the sector due to its rich history, ancient monuments, historical relics, and unique nature.

Especially in the Kitob, Shahrisabz, Yakkabog', G'uzor, and Qarshi districts, many examples of our national heritage are found. To develop tourism, there are many unexplored tourism routes and underutilized opportunities in Qashqadaryo. Several other measures aimed at developing the tourism potential of Qashqadaryo have been identified, and their full implementation will significantly increase the number of local and foreign tourists coming to the region and boost the income of the population.

In the current difficult economic situation worldwide, it is necessary to support sectors that create more jobs and increase investment and exports. Tourism has great potential in this regard. Any investment directed toward this sector will yield returns. Each new job creates additional jobs in other sectors. To achieve this, it is essential to improve tourism infrastructure and create opportunities for tourists' arrival and attraction.

There are many historical, cultural, and picturesque places in our country. It is necessary to build tourism facilities and hotels based on them. Procedures must be

simplified to facilitate tourism business. In particular, a 3,000-hectare mountain skiing complex is being established between G'elon and Sarchashma villages in the Shahrisabz district by foreign investors. To attract tourists, it is necessary to improve road infrastructure and promote tourism.

It is necessary to establish a tourism cluster in the city of Shahrisabz and the Shahrisabz district. The 33 km Hisorak-G'elon and Hisorak-Sarchashma roads need to be widened and repaired. In this situation, the "Chiroqchi-Sho'rquduq" highway will improve, reducing travel time from Samarkand to Shahrisabz. The tourism potential around natural lakes is also underutilized. For example, there are no recreation facilities along the Sechanko'l and Achinko'l lakes in the Mirishkor district. The Aydar-Arnasoy lakes system provides very favorable conditions for hunting and ecotour.

Discussion and Results

Thus, we have analyzed the literature and found that the Qashqadaryo region has significant tourism potential. However, if we focus on one of the main areas of attention, namely the Shahrisabz district, it is considered to have extremely high tourism potential. On the other hand, regions like G'ilon, Hisorak, and Miroqi have poorly developed tourism infrastructure, which affects the number of tourists visiting these areas. Several reasons can be cited for this:

- The road infrastructure is inadequate.
- Communication facilities are lacking.
- There is no availability of modern transportation.

However, it is difficult to imagine tourism infrastructure without modern computer technologies. Timely information and communication about news are integral parts of tourism. Currently, tourists' demand to use the internet and other modern technologies indicates the extent of the tourism infrastructure. Today, this issue has been resolved through computer technologies, including visas and credit

cards. Information services are crucial for both tourists and their organizers in tourism infrastructure. Tourists need maps of the places they are visiting and road schematics. Given these issues, improving tourism infrastructure in these areas will be challenging.

Solution: We can consider the solutions to these problems relatively straightforward because one of the main issues in tourist areas is transportation. Thus, we need to take a historical perspective to address these problems. In ancient times, people traveled to these places even without transportation means, relying on animals such as horses and donkeys, which were connected to carts, making the journey quite enjoyable. We can understand the advantages of such transportation means better through this scheme.

Diagram 1: Positive Aspects of Using Animal-Pulled Transportation

That is, if we utilize this system for transportation over long distances, for example, on the main routes ranging from 3-4 km, it would be quite effective. To comment on the table:

Low Cost—this primarily leads to minimal expenditure and, most importantly, does not harm the ecological environment.

Enjoyment—this aspect allows for the organization of various games and provides tourists with psychological energy.

Long Duration—this section enables us to keep tourists engaged for a longer period, during which we can sell them various additional services.

Investment—this is the most critical part, as we can profit from selling our services, and additionally, it provides local residents with job opportunities and a source of income.

References

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026.” PF-60. – Tashkent, January 28, 2022. Source: <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-5841063>
2. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Measures for Developing and Promoting Barrier-Free Tourism Infrastructure in the Republic of Uzbekistan.” PQ-20. – Tashkent, January 12, 2024. Source: <https://lex.uz/docs/6759708>
3. Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Further Supporting and Developing the Tourism Sector in Kashkadarya Region.” 112. – Tashkent, March 1, 2021. Source: <https://lex.uz/docs/-5316745>
4. N.S. Morozov, M.A. Morozov, A.D. Chudnovsky, M.A. Zhukova, L.A. Rodigin. *Information Support for Tourism: Textbook* / – Moscow: Federal Agency for Tourism, 2014. – 288 pages.
5. V.F. Ikonnikov, M.N. Sadovskaya. *Information Technologies in the Tourism Industry: Textbook and Methodological Guide* / – Minsk: RIPO, 2014. – 78 pages.
6. <https://tourlib.net/> - Online Tourist Library.
7. Vayskulov, R., & Xushvaqtov, R. (2024). *The Role of Digital Technologies in the Development of Ecological Tourism in Uzbekistan. Prospects of National Tourism in New Uzbekistan*, 1(01).

8. Mamashoyev Asadbek, Xushvaqtoev Ramziddin, Qurbonov Jahongir. (2022). *The Potential of Eco and Gastro Tourism in the Bulung'ur District of Samarkand. Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 11, 230–236.
9. Turayev Javohir, Lutfullayev Sherzod, Xushvaqtoev Ramziddin. *Scientific and Practical Directions for Increasing the Competitiveness of Enterprises Providing Tourist Services*, 306-310.
10. Vayskulov, R. (2023). *The Importance of Using Slogans in Promoting Tourism Opportunities in Regions. Economics and Education*, 24(3), 440-444.
11. Yusupovna, S. N., & Alisher ugli, V. R. (2023, December). *Ways of Effective Using of Mobile Technologies in the Development of Recreational Tourism*. In *International Conference on Next Generation Wired/Wireless Networking* (pp. 12-20). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
12. Malika, K., & Ramazon, V. (2022). *The Role of Innovations in the Development of Tourism in the Regions. Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 29, 207-211.
13. Ramazon, V., & Nurbek, T. (2022). *Effective Use of Vehicle Transport Services in Strengthening the Tourist Infrastructure. Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 29, 169-173.